

HISTORICAL AND ARCHEOLOGICAL SCIENCES

CONSIDERATION REGARDING THE MOVEMENT OF VISARION SARAI

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Abstract

The upheaval of the monk Visarion Sarai is the most representative religious movement within the Romanian space. That determined us to analyse it and to opinate on it, along with other historians. This movement stands for the answer of the Orthodox Christians from Transylvania to the politics of Counter-reform and Catholic Reform of the Habsburg authorities.

Together with the penetration of the Reform in Transylvania, the popular belief of the Romanians from Ardeal has been hindered by the renewing measures of the Calvinists. The cult of the icons, the fasting and certain customs were affected. After the reintegration in the Habsburg space the old rite has been reintroduced, even in the newly founded United Church. A question arises: why, since the involvement of the Calvinists in the belief of the masses, towards which Romanians manifested a great sensitivity, and until 1744 there were no religious movements of such span and intensity?

We believe that the reaction was determined by the Bishopric of Karlowitz. Although the Serb Metropolitan system did not admit this, certain documentary testimonies, to which mass psychology specific arguments add up, prove this truth.

Keywords: Eastern law, calvinism, Catholic Reformation, Counter, religious movement, Visarion Sarai.

In order to understand the dynamics of interfaith relations in Transylvania, as well as the subsequent evolution of the Romanian Church in the second half of the 18th century, it is relevant to dwell on the period 1744-1754, a decade with multiple meanings for this Church and for Transylvanian Romanians.¹

Visarion Sarai's movement represents, from our point of view, the typical case of a religious movement in the Romanian space. This problem has been analyzed by several authors, including G. Bogdan-Duică², who even wrote a monograph dedicated to Visarion, then Silviu Dragomir in *Istoria desrobirii...*³ with a special part about this movement; David Prodan⁴; Keith Hitchins⁵; Nicolae Stoica de Hațeg⁶; I. Ionescu⁷ și Gheorghe Cotoșman⁸. However, we also allow ourselves to express some opinions regarding this movement.

The Habsburg offensive led to the reincorporation of Transylvania and the removal of Calvinist influence, by imposing the imperial policy of counter-reformation and Catholic reform. In Transylvania, the Greek Catholic Church was created in this sense, and the Orthodox Church as an institution was abolished. The majority of Transylvanian Romanians still had the popular faith, that archaic form of Christianity. In order to understand the phenomenon from the middle of the 18th century, we think it is necessary to recall some features of this belief.

Analysts of Romanian Christianity accredited the idea of a "land-based Christianity of a popular nature"⁹,

actually an accommodation of old magical beliefs and rituals to Christian ideology - "magical objects and rituals sometimes adopted a Christian nomenclature, often insinuated themselves into a Christian chronology, imitated or even borrowed the language, symbols and values of the Christian law, without really letting themselves be shaped by the evangelical faith"¹⁰. A fulfillment of these norms seemed sufficient, in the thinking of the Romanian peasant, to benefit from the advantages of Heaven. All the excesses and denigrations from this line did not seem to them to be an obstacle on the way to salvation, but the non-fulfillment of the norms was a real disaster for them, a religious emotion was born in their soul. Johan Huizinga said about religious emotion that it manifests itself in a double form: in the form of internalization and in the form of violent reactions, which "overwhelmed the people from time to time, when an itinerant preacher caused, with his words, to catch fire as some sticks are all the spiritual fuel"¹¹.

The year 1744 received multiple meanings for the history of Romanians in Transylvania. In the atmosphere of the religious movement, protesting against the Union, led by the monk Visarion Sarai, the convocation of the great synod took place by the bishop Inochentie Micu Klein, an event that culminated in the departure of the bishop to Vienna and then to Rome.¹²

Keith Hitchins, moved the explanation from the political and confessional factor to the psychological and spiritual one, coming to define the spiritual climate

¹ Stanciu, Hitchins, Dumitran, 2009, p.23.

² Duică, *Visarion Sarai*, Caransebeș, 1896.

³ Dragomir, 1920.

⁴ Prodan, 1967.

⁵ Hitchins, 1987.

⁶ Stoica de Hațeg, *Cronica Banatului*, Timișoara, 1981.

⁷ I. Ionescu, *Cuviosul Visarion Sarai în lumina Cronicii protopopului Nicolae Stoica din Mehadia* în B.O.R., LXXXIX(1971), nr. 9-10, p. 1030.

⁸ Gheorghe Cotoșman, *Eremitul Visarion Valahul*, în „*Mitropolia Banatului*“, XXX (1957), nr. 1-3.

⁹ Radosav, 1997, p.17.

¹⁰ Barbu, 1996, p.35.

¹¹ J. Huizinga, 1993, p. 308.

¹² Stanciu, Hitchins, Dumitran, 2009, p.28.

of the Romanian village, to capture the thinking of the Romanian peasant.¹³

A religious movement, launched in the middle of the 18th century under the leadership of Visarion Sarai, could not be born out of nowhere. The factors that triggered this phenomenon acted on a latent fund, a fund that was formed during a century and a half, starting from 1600 and ending in 1744. The period is characterized by two segments: the first is the interval 1600-1692/97, when Eastern law was subject to Calvinist pressure, and the second is the interval 1692/97-1744, when the pressures are Catholic.

The Calvinists subordinated the Transylvanian Orthodox hierarchy, even more than that, they imposed a change in the rite and popular belief, attacking the cult of icons, fasting, old traditions dressed in Christian garb, etc.. These changes, especially visible among the people, they could not remain without consequences at the attitudinal level - the Orthodox hierarchy expressed its opposition to the face, through the Synod of Iași and Sava Brancovici; in the case of the Romanian peasants, we are convinced that they, individually, created virtual real religious uprisings, which were repressed in their subconscious waiting for the external impulse that would value them. So the Calvinist century provided favorable conditions for the outbreak of a religious protest movement. From the confessional point of view the conditions were much more favorable in this first period of time, compared to the first half of the 18th century, when the rite and everything related to the Eastern tradition had returned to normal. Two questions naturally arise: why until 1744 there were no religious movements of the intensity and expansion that Visarion Sarai's movement had, and then that of Sofronie din Ciocara? And why was Visarion's movement of such intensity and extent? We will try to answer these two questions in the following. The reasons why a religious movement did not break out in the Calvinist century are, we believe, at least three.

First of all, in this period there is no mention of a charismatic figure who preached against the imposed changes, a figure who was supported, from outside or inside, by a church or political leader, as happened with Visarion .

Secondly, the international political context was different, Transylvania was basically ruled by Protestants. The end of the century, however, brought a new configuration to the region: Transylvania came under Habsburg jurisdiction, and Parthium and Banat, although they also came under Habsburg obedience, were not in the same situation as Transylvania - the imperial interest in the area was different, the orthodoxy of the Serbs, in fact their military strength was useful to Vienna. In this context, the Serbian metropolitan had become, with the help of the Court, the leader of the Orthodox in the area, a leader who would always try to

increase his jurisdictional limits, thanks to the ecclesiastical, material and political power with which he had been invested through the Illyrian privileges.

Thirdly, we would also add a possible pact between the local Romanian elite and the Calvinists, a pact which will be broken after the union, in favor of a pact with the new power, and in southern Transylvania in favor of maintaining ties with Wallachia.

After the moment of unification, in fact, even during the negotiations in Vienna, part of the Romanian elite protested against this move. While Atanasie Anghel was still in Vienna, in March 1701, the great merchant from Sibiu, Pater Ianăș, wrote to the metropolitan to protest¹⁴. Another protest action took place at the installation ceremony of Athanasius, at the cathedral in Alba Iulia. Then the representatives of the residents of Brasov loudly demonstrated their opposition, being finally removed from the court, in order to then submit a written protest¹⁵. Gavril Nagyszegi also had the intention to revitalize Orthodoxy, by reopening closed churches and by promoting the divine service in accordance with the old faith¹⁶. To these actions is added the reaction of the Patriarchs of Constantinople and Jerusalem, as well as that of the Metropolitan of Wallachia.

The common denominator of these protests is that they represent a position of the elites and not the masses. All these, however, failed without any effect. The Transylvanian Orthodox Church remained without a hierarchical structure, probably due to the fact that the masses of believers were not trained in these protest actions. However, a small part of the people must have known about these actions, especially those in the cities where these protests were conceived and those who were near these cities. The latent fund created since the previous century at the level of the common people, continued to be excited from the outside, with a low intensity, however, until 1744, when it would reach the psychological peak necessary for a qualitative change. Among these excitements, less important in bringing to the surface the instinct of self-defense, but still having the role of maintaining the state of psychological tension at the individual level, we list: the investigations of the Diet of 1699, the propaganda of Ioan Patachi, the takeover of the church in Făgăraș by united, the activity of the monasteries, of the numerous hermitages, as well as other local movements prior to Visarion's.

From the statements of the peasantry, on the occasion of the investigations in 1699, there is evidence of Orthodox solidarity, of the spiritual unity of the Romanian believers¹⁷. From the statements of the peasantry, on the occasion of the investigations in 1699, there is evidence of Orthodox solidarity, of the spiritual unity of the Romanian believers¹⁸. Predominant is the refusal of the villages to accept any change in the field of religious spirituality: "until the end of life", "until death", "if someone disturbs them in the religion they have been in until now, they are ready to leave for another

¹³ *Ibidem*.

¹⁴ Prodan, 1984, p.131, Iorga, 1989, p. 237.

¹⁵ Iorga, *Istoria bisericii românești*, vol.II, p. 35; Idem, *Istoria românilor din Ardeal și Ungaria*, I- II, București 1989, p.238; Idem, *Sate și preoți*, p.192, 194; Lupaș, 1995, p.110.

¹⁶ Hitchins, 1987, p.42.

¹⁷ Greta Miron, *Unirea religioasă și mentalul rural transilvănean*, în vol. *Viață privată și mentalități colective*, Oradea- Cluj- Napoca, 1995- 1996, p.165.

¹⁸ *Ibidem*, p.165.

country", "I don't change the law inherited from my parents and my religion, which the Muscals and Greeks hold, that's why I want to die", "I don't change my religion, which is the same as that of the Muscals and Greeks"¹⁹. The investigations brought to the knowledge of the people the intentions to change the denomination. We saw that the reaction was generally negative, but here it must be taken into account that the investigations were coordinated by Protestants, who could channel the answers in a certain sense. Anyway, the main idea that we retain here is that the people became aware of the unification action, a particularly important aspect because until 1744 there was no action of such magnitude, which would have informed the people of the union with Rome.

Another role in maintaining the state of tension and even increasing it was the action of Ioan Patachi. He was appointed united bishop two years after the death of Athanasius Anghel. He distanced himself from the people by his sermons in the Latin rite. He held to the Catholic dogmas to the point of exaltation, through travelers he propagated these dogmas, having violent discussions with the priests he met. The grief of the people increased because of these facts. The takeover of the church in Făgăraș, a church that had been built with the support of Constantin Brâncoveanu, must also have had a negative aspect. The punishments and monetary fines that Bishop Patachi gave to those who refused to join the union should also be mentioned here.²⁰

What greatly supported the old law was the large number of monasteries with two or three monks, often scholars, painters, small villages that were spread throughout the country²¹. Their role in the pro-Orthodox struggle was recognized by the state, through the actions of destruction at the beginning of the seventh decade. The state of tension accumulated over time was expressed on the surface in the years 1726-1727, when believers rose against the priests in the villages who publicly expressed their adherence to the union, however the resistance to the union remained sporadic and isolated²², this is because all the necessary elements for the constitution of a psychological mass had not been fulfilled, what was more important was missing, the "hypnotist" otherwise the ground was prepared.

At the individual level the fund has been maintained based on primary information about the union, maybe even rumors, it will become collective by contagion. The movement against the union was also supported with the help of books, priests and monks ordained across the Carpathians. Ștefan Meteș, in the Relations of the Romanian Church from Transylvania with the Romanian Principalities in the 18th century, presents a list of priests who crossed the mountains to be ordained²³. Against them, the government took expulsion measures in 1744 and 1746, which was practically impossible to put into practice. These monks prepared the ground for Visarion and Sophronie. Their urge could not be other than the defense of the ancestral

law, the preservation of the old faith. The most important is the help coming from the Karlowitz Metropolitanate. The documentary testimonies of the time reflect a constant concern of the Serbian metropolitans and their subordinate hierarchs, regarding the fate of the Orthodox believers in the provinces exposed to unionist pressures, through the presence of canonical visits, pastoral letters and spiritual edification and strengthening of the Orthodox conscience, through repeated requests and protests addressed to the authorities. Under the authority of the metropolitan system from Karlowitz were Banat and Crișana, for a while even Oltenia.

In this way the ground was prepared, all that was needed was a charismatic character to light the flame. Transylvanian Orthodoxy was waiting for the solution from outside, internally nothing could be done without outside support. In the spring of 1744, an "apostle" or perhaps the prophet that the believers wanted in their imaginations had appeared, he was Visarion Sarai. This monk will change the attitude of the Transylvanians of Eastern faith, especially those from the southern parts. Violence is henceforth the main characteristic in comparison with the previous lethargic state, violence towards the union with Rome, in general, and in particular, towards the united priests. Authoritarianism and intolerance are a general feature of all categories of crowds, but it is well known how intolerant religious beliefs are and how they control souls - during Visarion's movement intolerance was undoubtedly present, but it was a primitive act of conservation, extreme conservatism manifested itself then.

Visarion Sarai's penetration into Transylvania caused, by impact and mental contagion, a vast and lasting popular action, always growing, against the Union. There were expulsions of united priests, taking of churches and parish property, installation of non-united priests, simultaneously with violence against united priests. In many parts of Hunedoara, Alba, Făgăraș, the Land of the Kings, it was almost impossible to speak of the Union.

The provincial authorities, forced to face a reality that was difficult for them to understand, summoned to intervene to bring peace to the country and obliged to explain to the central power what happened in the territory, concluded: "the wandering Eastern monk Visarion" began to accuse the Roman Catholic Church of idolatry. Other offenses were added: the looting of churches, the desecration of communion consecrated by the united priests and the myrrh consecrated by the united bishop, the ordination of priests outside the province and functioning without seeking confirmation from the united bishop, the abuses and superstitious practices of the "new" priests regarding sacraments, rebutting the idea of the invalidity of the sacraments received from the united priests. The opinion of the Aulice Chancellery, for example, was formulated and focused on highlighting the crimes committed by non-unionists against His Majesty's religion, making themselves worthy of punishment not because of religious

¹⁹ *Ibidem*, p.166.

²⁰ Bariț, 1993, p. 346.

²¹ Iorga, 1989 b, p.252-253.

²² Hitchens, 1987, p.42.

²³ Meteș, 1928.

choices, but of conspiracies, contempt for imperial orders, correspondence with "the Turkish provinces" etc²⁴.

The question we tried to answer is what determined such a rapid (in the only 40 days spent in Transylvania, between March 11-April 20, 1744) and devastating influence of the peregrine monk on the Romanian population?²⁵

The origin of this hermit seems to have been Vlach, more specifically Aromanian from Bosnia, belonging to the Ciurcia or Tiurcia family²⁶. Silviu Dragomir simply calls him a Serb²⁷.

If his origin is clear, the language in which he preached for the Transylvanians raises some problems for historians, dividing them into two camps. The camp that claims that this language was Serbian includes the following: G. Bogdan-Duică, P. Maior, S. Dragomir, A. Bunea²⁸, G. Barit, K. Hitchins. Among those who claim that the language was Romanian, we mention N. Iorga, Gh. Cotoșman, but especially N. Stoica de Hațeg. In support of the Serbian language, K. Hitchins states: "the fact that he spoke in Serbian, which was related to Old Slavonic, the language of the liturgy in the Romanian church until the second half of the 17th century, must have given his words an additional charge"²⁹. In the Chronicle of the Archpriest of Hațeg it is said: "he spoke some Romanian because he was in Wallachia for a year..."³⁰. The path traveled by Visarion in Transylvania is also found in the Chronicle: "He came with the metropolitan's slobozena, with a parish priest not only in Carloviț and Novisade, but also in Timisoara and in Banat. And in Lugoj, with revelers, in Dobra, in Ardeal, in Deva he passed"³¹.

The image of the hermit in the eyes of the faithful was of great importance in triggering the movement, but to an even greater extent his sermons, short and penetrating, which were in accordance with the state of mind of the Romanian Orthodox. These two elements were preceded by rumors like: "he is a saint", "he entered Transylvania as a saint", "he is an angel descended from heaven". The image of the monk created a strong impression on the crowds. His portrait is described by the bishop Vichientie Popovici and by the father of the dean of Hațeg: "...a monk came, ugly in head and feet, old with a bad belt..., with a ragged race, in opinci, a fluffy monk's hat, gray-haired, emaciated, toothless in his mouth..., seeing that he does not eat or drink until after noon, at the quindie, taking out from his breast the bag of lentils and a small pot in which nine lentil grains were boiling with water. The juice was sipped, the grains, chewing one by one, swallowed them"³².

The leader plays a considerable role in the coordination of the mass, he is usually not a thinker, but a man of action. Such people are recruited especially among

the exalted, among those who believe to the extreme. Visarion was such a character, he was an ascetic monk, his way of dressing and feeding were suggestive to the crowd. In this type of people and the instinct of preservation is null, the only reward they want is martyrdom - Visarion knew that he could be condemned for his action.

His short and penetrating sermons, perhaps it would be more correct to use the term target sermons, had a greater role than the other elements. This is because they questioned the afterlife of the living as well as those who had been buried by the united priests. The "apostle" said he was sorry to think that so many souls would die forever. He spoke of those who united as of some who sold their souls, "for to them the loosing of the dead is not loosing, but damnation; they pay the parastases, memorials and sarinderes in the desert to wicked people: to the grandchildren; the baptism of children has no value, and that is why it hurts more than the souls of children, which must grow in union" [Silviu Dragomir, 1920, vol.I, p.138.]. He also taught the people how to believe in God, in the Virgin Mary, in Saint Nicholas, to pray, to keep four fasts a year, not to commit sins, not to be deceived by the united peoples, not to believe in the pope from Rome, that they believe. "Lula, duham, with the smoke was offensive, on Wednesdays and Fridays fish food was prohibited. In some cases the pepper stopped it because it makes people thirsty and people get drunk and so they commit sins and the Lord beats them. Crăiesi and its laws should be faithful"³³.

A simple analysis of these target sermons highlights the fact that he marches on the main pillars of popular belief: baptism, marriage, fasting, burial and eternal life. Due to the fact that they were mediated by "nepopes", not by Eastern priests, they had no value. In this way, the perspective of eternal life was broken, the believer, who diligently prepared for eternity all his earthly life, was going to be sent to hell. Visarion's sermons evoke in the minds of the people the image of eternal fire, which awaits them, since heaven cannot receive them because of the non-fulfillment of the norm, they also evoke an analogy between the devils and the united priests, who pushed them into hell. The orator in an intimate communion with the mass of people, seeks to evoke the images that seduce it, two or three phrases that succeed in subduing the masses and convincing them. Visarion knew this, or those who sent him, instructing him in this, his phrases are moving and have correspondences in the imagination of the common man, an imagination for the most part, in that age, subject to the divine.

The reaction of the mass of believers, caught up in this mental contagion, is described in the Chronicle, but also in the official acts of the Government, of the united

²⁴ Documentul 251(11 ianuarie 1749); 281 (post 14 martie 1749); 311 (13 septembrie 1750); 313 (ante 7 noiembrie 1750) apud Stanciu, Hitchins, 2009, p.30-31.

²⁵ Keith Hitchins, *Religia și conștiința națională românească în Transilvania în secolul XVIII* apud Stanciu, Hitchins, Dumitran, 2009, p.28.

²⁶ Gheorghe Cotoșman, *Emeritul în „Mitropolia Banatului“*, XXX (1957), nr. 1-3, p. 107.

²⁷ Dragomir, 1920, vol.I, p.156.

²⁸ Bunea, 1902.

²⁹ Hitchins, 1987, p.45.

³⁰ Stoica de Hațeg, 1981, p.185-186.

³¹ Dragomir, 1920, vol.I, p.138.

³² Stoica de Hațeg, 1981, p.185.

³³ Stoica de Hațeg, 1920, p.186.

clergy and in those of the Catholic state. Everywhere, from Lipova, Dobra, Orăștie, Săliște and until he was arrested, Visarion was given a special welcome: the bells of all the churches were rung, as on a holiday announcing the arrival of the "saint". "The three thousand Romanian workers put to work on the Pacaț field, in the region of Timișoara, leave their scythes and run forward and in the footsteps of the saint, determined not to leave him until the hour of their salvation and release from the slavery of the new pharaoh rings. crueler and more relentless than that of biblical Egypt"³⁴.

On May 6, 1744, the Governor of Transylvania made a decision in which a small picture of the movement provoked by Visarion is presented: "A foreigner named Visarion, a wandering and deceptive wanderer, in this country, the one who did not even get legitimized, whose social category belongs to, he deceived the stupid Wallachians so much that some of them and the whole village did not want to attend the united churches and listen to the priests, something that made the Government wonder, how can the Romanians be so agitated at the word of such a vile and miserable country wind. Everything that happened is against God and against the country"³⁵.

The mobilization of the masses of believers, in order to preserve their ancient faith, also led to a mobilization of the authorities, their purpose being of course the opposite. The authorities wanted to preserve the union at all costs. If the Romanians, who formed the base of the social pyramid, had no economic or social interest in this movement, only a purely spiritual one, the Habsburg authorities pursued such an interest. At the level of the imperial leaders and the local ones there was a certain fear, they were afraid that this movement would not turn into a social one. We can say that the panic also reached this level, it was of course a panic of a completely different nature. It took shape in the measures proposed by the united clergy, the Catholic state and Maria Teresa, by requesting the publication of that proclamation to the people and by sending the Ruthenian Bishop of Muncaci to Transylvania, in the winter of 1745-1746, to make a report on the state of the union. Bishop Manuil Olsavzky's report presented the most important leaders of this movement, described the violent acts committed by the Romanians and recommended harsh means for the "eradication" of the non-united³⁶.

Therefore, Visarion was the expected "apostle", he indicated the way forward, which the ship struggling between the waves could not find. This ship had to fight the storm. The mobilization of the Orthodox believers against the union was possible thanks to his presence. Without the presence of a charismatic figure, similar to this monk, almost a century and a half passed in which the ancestral law had received especially many and serious blows. During this period, the quantitative conditions necessary for the qualitative leap were met. A well-instrumented action is required for this step.

As I said, guides are not thinkers, but people of action, they can only exercise their function on the condition that they themselves are directed and motivated

by something, that they feel above themselves a man, an idea, to follow a precisely drawn direction - that something was the Karlowitz Metropolis and probably the Mountain Metropolis. How did Visarion manage to coordinate the crowd of believers? By affirmation, by repetition, by contagion, relying on imitation, on his prestige. Affirmation is a sure way by which an idea is made to penetrate the minds of multitudes. More concise and without arguments is imposed better. However, arguments were presented, that "divine reasoning", affecting the action in a positive sense. A statement has no affective flow unless it is constantly repeated in the same terms - at Visarion we find the same expressions everywhere. The thing said and repeated many times ends up imposing itself in the deep areas of the unconscious, where the motivations of our actions are elaborated. To these is added that century and a half of repression of the instinct of self-defense, of fighting against those who were affecting their Eastern faith.

Through these lines, we believe that we have provided an additional argument to the idea of the involvement of the Karlowitz Metropolitanate in the action of Visarion Sarai from Transylvania, although this institution has denied any involvement.

References

1. Barbu, 1996 Daniel Barbu, *Scrisoare pe nisip. Timpul și privirea în civilizația românească a secolului XVIII*, București, 1996.
2. Bariț, 1993 G. Bariț, *Părși alese din istoria Transilvaniei pe două sute de ani în urmă*, ed. II, vol. I, Brașov, 1993
3. Bunea, 1902 Augustin Bunea, *Episcopii Petru Pavel Aron și Dionisie Novacovici*, Blaj, 1902.
4. Cotoșman, 1957 Gheorghe Cotoșman, *Eremitul Visarion Valahul*, în „*Mitropolia Banatului*“, XXX (1957), nr. 1-3.
5. Dragomir, 1920 Silviu Dragomir, *Istoria desrobirii religioase a românilor din Ardeal în secolul al XVIII-lea*, vol. I, Sibiu, 1920.
6. Duică, 1896 G. Bogdan-Duică, *Visarion Sarai*, Caransebeș, 1896.
7. Hitchens, 1987 Keith Hitchens, *Conștiință națională și acțiune politică la românii din Transilvania(1700-1868)*, Cluj Napoca, Editura Dacia, 1987.
8. Ionescu, 1971 I. Ionescu, *Cuviosul Visarion Sarai în lumina Cronicii protopopului Nicolae Stoica din Mehadia* în B.O.R., LXXXIX(1971), nr. 9-10, p.1030.
9. Iorga, 1989, a N. Iorga, *Istoria românilor din Ardeal și Ungaria*, I- II, București, 1989.
10. Iorga, 1989, b N. Iorga, *Sate și preoți din Ardeal*, București, 1989.
11. Iorga, 2012 Nicolae Iorga, *Istoria bisericii românești*, vol. II, București, 2012.
12. Huizinga J. Huizinga, *Amurgul evului mediu*, București, 1993.
13. Prodan, 1967 David Prodan, *Supplex Libellus Valachorum*, București, 1967.

³⁴ Gheorghe Cotoșman, *Emeritul* în „*Mitropolia Banatului*“, XXX (1957), nr. 1-3, p. 106.

³⁵ Silviu Dragomir, 1981, vol.I, p.144.

³⁶ *Ibidem*, p.166-167.

14. Proda, 1984 David Prodan, *Supplex Libellus Valachorum. Din istoria formării națiunii române*, București, 1984.
15. Lupaș, 1995 I. Lupaș, *Istoria bisericească a românilor ardeleni*, Cluj-Napoca, 1995.
16. Meteș, 1928 Ștefan Meteș, *Relațiile bisericii românești din Ardeal cu Principatele române în veacul al XVIII-lea*, Sibiu, 1928.
17. Miron, 1995- 1996 Greta Miron, *Unirea religioasă și mentalul rural transilvănean*, în vol. *Viață privată și mentalități colective și imaginar social în Transilvania*, Cluj- Napoca- Oradea, 1995- 1996.
18. Radosav, 1997 Doru Radosav, *Sentimentul religios la români*, Cluj-Napoca, 1997.
19. Stoica de Hațeg, 1981 Nicolae Stoica de Hațeg, *Cronica Banatului*, Timișoara, 1981.
20. Stanciu, Hitchins, Dumitran, 2009 Laura Stanciu, Keith Hitchins, Daniel Dumitran, *Despre Biserica românilor din Transilvania. Documente externe(1744-1754)*, Cluj-Napoca, Editura Mega, 2009.